

6G-SANDBOX: Technology Validation and Measurement Campaigns for Non-Terrestrial Networks

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Abstract — 6G candidate technologies and components, require early validation on flexible and open experimentation infrastructures. Such infrastructures are also required to demonstrate 6G benefits in terms of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVIs). In this context, this paper introduces the concept of Trial Networks, i.e., the abstraction of the resources and the capabilities of a testbed, under a common format and description that allows zero-interaction with the platform administrator and automatic reservation of resources during experimentation. Major effort is allocated to one of the most promising domains of the 6G era of communication, i.e., the Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN).

Keywords— 6G testbed; automatic experimentation; Non-Terrestrial Networks..

I. INTRODUCTION

At the dawn of the new era in telecommunications, the principles of 6G networks and services are being designed, while a disruptive vision regarding the socioeconomic impact of 6G is being articulated in direct relation to the Sustainable Development Goals, formulated by the UN [1]. Initial expectations on 6G have been, for example, voiced by the European 5G Infrastructure Association (5G IA) [2], and the ITU [3], where a convergence of digital, physical, and human domains is envisioned. On this revolutionary path, the contribution of experimentation facilities for validating emerging 6G technologies will be crucial. These facilities will help organizations to dynamically respond to the 6G challenges and expectations.

Already, the potential of experimentation facilities has been demonstrated in the context of 5G, by pan-European facilities [4], such as 5GENESIS, 5G-VINNI, or 5G-EVE. Those facilities supported the 5G digital transformation and the conduction of trials for innovative services and applications. In the beyond-5G era, the key objectives of the European Smart Networks and Services (SNS) research and innovation program are formulated around the development of experimentation

infrastructures for validation of 6G technologies and use cases. In this context, the 6G-SANDBOX project¹ will provide an open facility for the validation of new technologies towards 6G as part of the emerging European 6G ecosystem.

This paper describes i) the main principles of the 6G-SANDBOX facility by presenting key architectural and technological aspects that the project adopts, and ii) the approach that is adopted for the integration of NTN and the involvement of those networks in technology validation and measurement campaigns.

II. PRINCIPLES OF THE 6G-SANDBOX FACILITY

Architectural approach

The project addresses the need for an experimentation facility that guarantees Modularity, Openness, Reusability, Innovation, and Sustainability (MORIS). *Modularity* is supported through the “infrastructure as a code” approach for creating the experimentation infrastructures that compose the testbed and also through the adoption of standardized APIs and API managers. The *openness* guarantee is introduced at multiple levels, from opening up the experimentation results to releasing innovative software developments and integrations to an open repository, named the Open 6G Library. To maximize *reusability*, common testing methodologies and test templates are adopted to produce self-defined and easily-comparable KPI/KVI results. Based on the concept of Trial Networks, as explained later in this section, the facility is *innovative* by design; however, there are specific innovative aspects at the connectivity, management, and application/use case levels that are presented as project ambitions later in this section. Finally, regarding the *sustainability* factor, the evolution beyond the project lifetime tailored with i) the evolution plans of its build-in components (especially the experimentation toolbox form Keysight and the developments that will be open sourced) and ii) the tight engagement with program level objectives of SNS JU. Fig. 1 illustrates the 6G-SANDBOX concept, while key

¹ <https://6g-sandbox.eu/>

architectural components are further elaborated in the subsections below.

The Trial Networks concept

Building and exposing experimentation platforms for 5G has been addressed by 5G PPP projects [4] and by other international and national programs like FIRE in Europe and PAWR in the US. However, these previous approaches have two main obstacles for fulfilling the requirements expected by experimenters in the beyond 5G and 6G domains. The first obstacle is that the experimenter does not have access to the internal configuration of the network components; for instance, to test new AI/ML algorithms for any optimization at the network or service level, a fine-tuning of the underlay communication and compute infrastructure is required by the infrastructure owner. The second obstacle is the lack of capability to run medium- or long-term experiments, or even complete projects, without the need of time-consuming manual reconfiguration and provisioning of the setup from time to time. Both obstacles are related to the poor capability of the underlay infrastructure to automatically support pure automation and multi-tenancy in a secured way. By addressing both of these obstacles, a more *industrialized (automated-repeatable)* way for 6G experimentation services is provided, with benefits for both experimenters and experimentation platform providers.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Architecture of 6G-SANDBOX

In this context, 6G-SANDBOX provides the means for the generation of testbeds in the form of *Trial Networks*. A Trial Network (TN) is defined as a fully configurable, manageable, and controllable network that combines virtual, physical and emulated resources (i.e., digital twins) and enables experiments for validating 6G technologies and measure 6G KPIs. Instances of Trial Networks might be offered targeting specific network domains and technologies, while within the 6G-SANDBOX project, end-to-end TNs will be offered by the four experimentation platforms of the project. By its definition a TN is an abstraction of an actual testbed, and is able to be reserved through multi-tenancy by experimenters that have secure access to the TN.

III. INTEGRATING NTN IN EXPERIMENTATION FACILITIES

One of the key technologies that will take part of 6G development will be NTN communications [6]. Release 17 of 3GPP is a significant achievement for the satellite industry, as it

will be the first land-based standard to natively include a space component through the Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN). This release specifically concentrates on the transparent satellite use case, where the satellite serves as a transparent repeater with limited on-board 5G implemented functions. 6G will enhance the existing attributes and fully integrate them within the future 6G standard.

For this reason, 6G-SANDBOX project has included a LEO Satellite connection as part of Málaga Testbed, and this Satellite connection will be included as part of TNs offered to experimenters.

Fig. 2. Illustration of the Malaga platform

Telefónica will provide this LEO satellite link using OneWeb provider [7] and will connect this satellite constellation to an Edge node located in Madrid at the Peñuelas Central Office that Telefónica has in the city centre. This satellite link integrated in the TNs will let experimenters tests the TNs with experiments that will have components deployed at Madrid Edge node connected via LEO satellite to the 5G Advanced infrastructure in the Málaga testbed.

Moreover, 6G-SANDBOX has signed a MOI with the European Space Agency to exploit together the research opportunities in 6G for NTN sharing 6G-SANDBOX infrastructure in all testbeds.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The 6G-SANDBOX project has been funded by European Commission (GA number 101096328).

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